

POLY (VINYL ALCOHOL)/GRAPHENE OXIDE FIBER PREPARED BY GEL PROCESS

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1 Introduction

In recent years, nanotechnology is expected to make a major contribution to the various fields of industries, and many achievements were made by the stimulated researches and developments of the nanotechniques. Nanocomposite, in which the filler have at least one dimension in nanoscale, was first discovered by Toyota Central R&D Labs., Inc. [1]. They prepared the nylon6/clay nanocomposite and revealed the significant improvements in the mechanical and thermal properties by the incorporation of clay. Since then, it has been demonstrated that polymer nanocomposites show superior properties than those of virgin polymers or conventional microfillers composites. For example, the increase in mechanical properties [2-4], thermal properties [5, 6] and gas-barrier properties [7] have been reported.

In the last few decades, nanocarbon materials have attracted a great deal of attention due to their unique properties. Fullerene, which consists of C₆₀ buckyballs, was first discovered in 1985 [8], followed by the discovery of carbon nanotube in 1991 [9]. Recently, in 2004, single-layered graphene was first isolated by Geim *et. al.* [10] and, in 2010, they were awarded the Nobel Prize in physics. Nowadays, graphene has been extensively studied as one of the hottest materials in various fields. It was revealed that graphene possesses excellent properties, such as Young's modulus of 1 TPa, ultimate strength of 130 GPa and the thermal conductivity of 5000 W/m·K [11, 12]. Because of its high performances, graphene has been expected to be a promising filler for polymer nanocomposites. In order to produce good interactions between graphene and polymer matrices, chemical modification of graphene has been widely conducted and rich varieties of graphene derivatives have been developed [13].

Among the graphene derivatives, chemically modified graphene derivatives are often processed from graphene oxide (GO). GO is produced during the process of the chemical preparation of graphene through the oxidation of graphite [14]. Thus GO possesses oxygen-containing functional groups on the base plane/edge of graphene. In general, conventional nanocarbon materials tend to form agglomerates and bundles due to van der Waals force between themselves. On the other hand, the oxygen-containing functional groups on the surface enable GO to readily disperse at nanoscale in water.

Recently, we reported that GO was highly dispersed in polymer matrices by using water as a processing medium. The polymer matrices used were poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) [15] and poly (vinyl alcohol) (PVA) [16], and they were hydrophobic polymer and hydrophilic polymer, respectively. It was revealed that the excellent properties, such as mechanical, thermal and barrier properties, were successfully imparted to the nanocomposites by the incorporation of GO.

Though the studies on the GO reinforced polymer nanocomposites have been widely made in all over the world, few studies have been made on the GO reinforced nanocomposite fiber. In this study, PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers were prepared in glass tube mold through gel process, followed by hot drawing. Compared to the conventional gel spinning of polymer based fibers, this technique can be said as simpler, cheaper and more environmentally friendly process. The structure and the properties of the drawn nanocomposite fibers were investigated.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

PVA powder (Poval-145, Kuraray Co. Ltd., Japan) with the degree of polymerization of 4500 and the

degree of saponification of 98–99 % was used. The GO aqueous suspension with 1 % w/w solid content was supplied from Mitsubishi Gas Chemical, Inc. GO was prepared by a method based on Hummers method [14]. Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), which was purchased from Wako Chemical Industry Ltd., was used as received.

2.2 Sample Preparation

GO aqueous suspension was diluted with distilled water and was mixed with DMSO (DMSO/distilled water = 80/20). PVA powder was added to the GO suspension and dissolved at 90 °C. The concentration of PVA in the suspension was 10 % w/w and the GO content was 0–1 % w/w against PVA. The PVA/GO suspension was sealed in a glass tube and cooled at -20 °C for 24 h. The gel fiber was taken out from the tube and soaked in ethanol for 12 h. After the solvent exchange, the gel fiber was dried at room temperature, followed by vacuum drying at 40 °C for 48 h. Subsequently, the fiber was drawn in an oven at 150 °C. The draw ratio (DR) was ranged from 1 (undrawn) to 50.

2.3 Characterization

The morphology of GO was studied using atomic force microscopy (AFM, Nano Navi Station/E-sweep, Seiko Instruments Inc.). A silicon cantilever probe was used in the tapping mode in air. The sample was prepared by spin-coating the diluted GO aqueous suspension on a silicon wafer. The Fourier transferred infrared (FTIR) spectrometry (Spectrum GX FTIR System I-KS, Perkin Elmer) was performed at a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹. The number of the accumulated scans was 10. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were conducted for the GO powder on an indium ingot using an ESCA-850 spectrometer (Shimadzu Co.). The GO aqueous suspension was dried at room temperature, followed by vacuum drying. MgK α radiation was generated at 8 kV and 30 mA.

Optical microscope (OPTIPHOT2-POL, Nikon Co., Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) was used to measure the diameter of the fibers. X-ray diffraction was performed using an X-ray diffractometer (Rigaku, RINT2100) equipped with Ni-filtered CuK α radiation. The X-ray beam was operated at 40 kV and 20 mA. The 2 θ scan data were collected at 0.02 degree intervals at a scanning speed of 1.0 degree/min. X-ray diffraction photographs were

used to obtain the azimuthal intensity distribution graph for the 101/10 $\bar{1}$ reflection of PVA. The degree of orientation (π) of PVA crystallites was calculated by the following equation (1):

$$\pi = \frac{180 - \text{FWHM}}{180} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where, FWHM is the full width at half maximum.

Tensile test was performed using Autograph AGS-1kND (Shimadzu Co., Kyoto, Japan) with the cross head speed of 2 mm/min. The initial length was 20 mm. The number of the test specimens was at least 10 for each sample.

The thermal decomposition temperature (T_d) was measured by a thermogravimeter (TG/DTA-220CU, Seiko Instruments Inc., Chiba, Japan) under nitrogen flow with a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The T_d was defined as the temperature at which the specimen had a 5 % w/w thermal weight loss. The melting point (T_m), the heat of fusion (ΔH_m) and the crystallinity (X_c) of PVA were determined by a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC-220CU, Seiko Instruments Inc., Chiba, Japan). Each sample was heated from the room temperature to 300 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under nitrogen flow.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Structure

Fig. 1 shows the AFM height image of GO (upper) and the height profile along the line (lower). In the height image, the wrinkles and folding were observed on the GO surface. Judging from the profile, the thickness of GO was 0.8–1.0 nm, indicating that the monolayer was successfully exfoliated. The average aspect ratio of GO was 3000.

Fig. 2 shows the FTIR spectrum of GO. In addition to the stretching vibration of an aromatic sp² carbon, aliphatic C–H stretching and deformation vibration appeared at 1622, 2915 and 1352 cm⁻¹, respectively [17]. These bands are derived from the graphene structure, which is the main backbone of GO. The bands corresponding to the oxygen-containing functional groups on the surface were also observed in the spectrum. The bands assigned as C=O stretching, C–OH bending and C–O stretching appeared at 1733 cm⁻¹, 1225 cm⁻¹ and 1075 cm⁻¹, respectively [18]. In addition, the band at 975 cm⁻¹ can be assigned as the symmetrical epoxy ring and the out-of-plane wagging of O–H–O [19]. The

hydroxyl groups, including adsorbed water, appeared at 3404 cm^{-1} (O–H stretching vibration) and 1622 cm^{-1} (O–H bending vibration) [20, 21]. The XPS analysis revealed that GO contained 27.8 atomic % of oxygen.

Fig. 3 shows the X-ray diffraction profiles of the drawn (DR=1, 50) PVA fibers and PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers with 1 % w/w GO loading. The characteristic peak of 001 reflection, which corresponding to the GO interlayer ($2\theta=10.1^\circ$), was not observed for the nanocomposite fibers with 1 % w/w GO loading. In our previous work [15], we observed the GO 001 reflection in the profile when the GO powder, obtained by drying the aqueous suspension, was physically mixed with the PVA powder using a mortar (GO content=1 % w/w). The presence of this reflection suggests the restacking of GO during the drying. Therefore, the lack of this reflection revealed that GO was exfoliated and highly dispersed at nanoscale in the PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers. In addition, the presence of water was found to be the key for the nanodispersion of GO in the nanocomposites.

Fig. 4 shows the X-ray diffraction photographs of the drawn (DR=1, 50) PVA fibers and PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers with 1 % w/w GO loading. The $101/10\bar{1}$ reflection of PVA clearly appeared in both the PVA fibers and the PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers. For the undrawn (DR=1) fibers, the reflection appeared as a homogeneous Debye-Scherrer ring, indicating the random orientation of the PVA crystallites. On the other hand, for the drawn fibers, the reflection focused on the equatorial direction. The drawn fibers with DR of 50 showed the reflection as a spot. This suggests that the PVA crystallites were highly oriented parallel to the drawn direction. Table 1 shows the diameter (D) of the drawn PVA fibers and nanocomposite fibers determined from the optical images and the degree of orientation (π) calculated from the azimuthal intensity distribution graph for the PVA $101/10\bar{1}$ reflection using the equation (1). The D value decreased with increasing of DR, while the π value increased with increasing of DR. It was revealed that the π value drastically increased at DR of 10, and slightly increased with further drawing. The π values of the drawn fibers with DR of 50 were found to reach to the almost full crystallites orientation of 97 % for both PVA fiber and nanocomposite fiber.

3.2 Properties

Fig. 5 shows the stress-strain curves of the undrawn (DR=1) PVA fiber and the PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers. The undrawn fibers showed the curves with yielding and plastic deformation, which is similar to that of the as-cast films in our previous study [15]. This was due to the random orientation of the PVA crystallites in the undrawn fibers. Compared with the Young's modulus (E) and the tensile strength (σ_{\max}) of the undrawn PVA fiber, those of the undrawn nanocomposite fibers increased by the incorporation of GO. This suggests that, as well as the as-cast nanocomposite films, excellent reinforcement effect of GO was exploited in the nanocomposite fibers due to the efficient stress transfer and the strong interaction between PVA and GO (Fig. 6).

Previously, the gel spun PVA nanocomposite fibers reinforced by single wall carbon nanotube (SWNT) were prepared by Zhang *et. al.* [22]. In this case, the fibers were prepared by conventional gel spinning process using a syringe pump and a syringe with a needle. During the gel spinning, shear stress was applied to the fibers, therefore, the fibers were drawn in the uniaxial direction. As a result, high mechanical properties were achieved even for the undrawn fibers. They showed that the E value increased from 25.6 GPa to 35.8 GPa (22 % increase) and the σ_{\max} value increased from 0.9 GPa to 1.1 GPa (40 % increase) by the incorporation of SWNT 3 % w/w.

On the other hand, Xu *et. al.* [23] drew the PVA/SWNT nanocomposite fibers after the gel spinning and revealed the remarkable increase in the mechanical properties by the hot-drawing. The drawn nanocomposite fiber with DR of 23 was found to show the E value of 36 GPa and the σ_{\max} value of 2.2 GPa with only 0.3 % w/w of SWNT loading, while the PVA fiber with DR of 26 showed the E value of 28 GPa and the σ_{\max} value of 1.7 GPa. These results indicate that the orientation arising from the hot-drawing had a large effect on the mechanical properties of the nanocomposite fibers with low filler contents.

Fig. 7 shows the stress-strain curves obtained from the tensile test of the drawn (DR=50) PVA fiber and the PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers. The drawn PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers also showed remarkable increases in the E value and the σ_{\max}

value. Fig. 8 shows E value and the σ_{\max} value of the drawn PVA fibers and PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers as a function of DR. Both the E value and the σ_{\max} value increased with the increasing of DR. The σ_{\max} value of the nanocomposite fiber with 1 % w/w GO loading was 1.4 GPa at DR of 50. As shown in Table 1, the π value of the PVA crystallites also showed a remarkable increase at DR of 10. Since the σ_{\max} value of the drawn fibers remarkably increased at DR of 10, it was suggested that the orientation of the PVA crystallites has a large effect on the σ_{\max} value of the drawn fibers. On the other hand, the E value constantly increased with DR of more than 10. The drawn PVA/GO nanocomposite fiber with DR of 50 was found to achieve the E value of 60 GPa, which was close to that of glass fiber, with only 1 % w/w GO loading. It was assumed that not only the PVA crystallites but also the GO sheets were oriented parallel to the drawn direction, which brought the effective stress transfer in the drawn nanocomposite fibers.

Fig. 9 showed the DSC curves of the drawn (DR=1, 50) PVA fibers and PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers with 1 % w/w GO loading. The T_m corresponding to the peak of the endotherm shifted to the higher temperature by the drawing. At the same time, the drawn fibers showed the sharp peak, indicating the increase in the X_c . Table 2 summarizes the T_m and the X_c of the drawn PVA fibers and the nanocomposite fibers determined from the DSC measurements. The X_c of PVA was calculated using the following equation (2):

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{w\Delta H_m^0} \quad (2)$$

where ΔH_m^0 is the heat of fusion for PVA crystal (161 J/g [24]) and w is the weight fraction of PVA. The X_c of the drawn fiber with DR of 50 was 20 % higher than that of undrawn (DR=1) fiber for both PVA fibers and nanocomposite fibers. In addition, the X_c of the nanocomposite fiber was found to be higher than that of the PVA fiber for every DR.

Previously, we showed that the X_c of the as-cast PVA/GO nanocomposites was increased by the incorporation of GO [15]. Similarly, it was suggested that GO act as a crystallization nucleus in the PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers, resulting in high X_c . Furthermore, the further crystallization was promoted by the presence of GO during the drawing,

together with the increase in the orientation of the PVA crystallites.

Fig. 10 shows the thermogravimetric traces of the drawn (DR=1, 50) PVA fibers and the PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers with 1 % w/w GO loading. The T_d of the fibers gradually increased with the increasing of DR. For the PVA fiber, the T_d increased 15 °C when it was drawn to DR of 50. On the other hand, the T_d for the drawn nanocomposite fiber with DR of 50 was 28 °C higher than that of the undrawn (DR=1) nanocomposite fiber. This indicates that the increase in T_d of the drawn fibers was largely attributed to the increase in X_c of PVA caused by the hot-drawing. In addition, the T_d of the nanocomposite fiber was found to be 10 °C higher than that of PVA fiber for every DR. This suggests that GO sheets hindered the decomposition products passing through the fiber, and at the same time, suppressed the PVA molecular motion due to the strong interaction. Therefore, the decomposition of the fiber was prevented and the high thermal stability was achieved for the nanocomposite fibers.

4 Conclusions

PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers were prepared by novel preparation method through gel process, which was simpler, cheaper and more environmentally friendly process than the conventional gel spinning.

It was revealed that GO was exfoliated and dispersed at nanoscale in the nanocomposite fibers. The X_c of PVA was effectively increased by the incorporation of GO and it was further increased by the hot-drawing. X-ray diffraction photographs revealed that the PVA crystallites were highly oriented parallel to the drawn direction by hot drawing. The drawn fibers with DR of 50 was found to achieve almost fully orientation ($\pi = 97$ %).

The drawn nanocomposites showed remarkable increase in the E value and the σ_{\max} value with increasing of DR due to the high orientation of the PVA crystallites, as well as high X_c . For example, the PVA/GO nanocomposite fiber with DR of 50 reached the E value of 60 GPa, which was close to that of glass fiber, with only 1 %w/w GO loading.

The thermal stability was effectively enhanced by the hot drawing of the nanocomposite fibers. The T_d of the drawn nanocomposite fibers increased with increasing of DR, and was found to be 10 °C higher than that of PVA fiber for every DR.

In summary, the excellent properties of GO were successfully imparted to the nanocomposite fibers and remarkably enhanced by the hot drawing.

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Figures and Tables

Fig. 1 AFM height image and height profile of GO.

Fig. 2 FT-IR spectrum of GO.

Fig. 3 X-ray diffraction profiles of drawn (DR=1, 50) PVA fiber and PVA/GO nanocomposite fiber.

Fig. 5 Stress-strain curves of undrawn (DR=1) PVA fiber and PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers.

Fig. 4 X-ray diffraction photographs of (A) undrawn (DR=1) PVA fiber and (B) PVA/GO nanocomposite fiber and (C) drawn (DR=50) PVA fiber and (D) PVA/GO nanocomposite fiber.

Fig. 6 Schematic model of the interaction between PVA and GO.

Fig. 7 Stress-strain curves of drawn (DR=50) PVA fiber and PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers.

Fig. 9 DSC curves of drawn (DR=1, 50) PVA fiber and PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers (1 % w/w).

Fig. 8 Young's modulus and tensile strength of drawn PVA fibers and PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers as a function of draw ratio.

Fig. 10 Thermogravimetric traces of drawn (DR=1, 50) PVA fibers and PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers (1 % w/w).

Table 1 Diameter (D), degree of orientation (π) and mechanical properties of drawn PVA fibers and PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers (1 % w/w).

	DR	D	π	E	σ_{\max}	ϵ_{\max}
	-	μm	%	GPa	GPa	%
PVA	1	393 ± 6	20.2	3.6 ± 1.0	0.05 ± 0.01	33.2 ± 2.5
	10	126 ± 5	95.1	11.3 ± 0.5	0.57 ± 0.06	14.9 ± 2.0
	20	106 ± 7	95.4	14.8 ± 1.0	0.99 ± 0.09	14.0 ± 1.8
	30	96 ± 9	96.2	18.3 ± 0.6	1.01 ± 0.12	11.1 ± 2.2
	40	89 ± 9	96.2	36.5 ± 0.6	1.08 ± 0.19	8.5 ± 0.9
	50	82 ± 5	96.3	39.8 ± 1.1	1.13 ± 0.13	8.1 ± 1.4
PVA/GO 1%w/w	1	393 ± 10	37.4	8.7 ± 1.1	0.07 ± 0.01	15.7 ± 2.3
	10	114 ± 8	95.2	22.8 ± 1.2	1.03 ± 0.07	12.9 ± 1.9
	20	100 ± 9	96.3	30.5 ± 0.9	1.18 ± 0.14	11.1 ± 1.4
	30	92 ± 6	96.3	40.5 ± 1.0	1.16 ± 0.08	8.9 ± 2.1
	40	87 ± 7	96.4	48.8 ± 1.2	1.19 ± 0.08	7.7 ± 2.0
	50	82 ± 4	97.2	60.0 ± 0.6	1.39 ± 0.10	7.3 ± 1.7

Table 2 Thermal properties, heat of fusion (ΔH_m) and the crystallinity (X_c) of drawn PVA fibers and PVA/GO nanocomposite fibers (1 % w/w).

	DR	T_d	T_m	ΔH_m	X_c
	-	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	J/g	%
PVA	1	275	228	86	53
	10	279	232	97	61
	20	280	233	105	65
	30	287	235	109	68
	40	288	235	112	70
	50	290	235	119	74
PVA/GO 1%w/w	1	280	229	91	57
	10	287	230	98	61
	20	290	233	107	66
	30	300	234	110	68
	40	298	235	119	76
	50	308	235	126	78